

MICROCHIP MARKING RECOGNITION AND IDENTIFICATION USING A COMPUTER VISION SYSTEM MATHEMATICAL MODEL

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ABSTRACT

The article considers a microcircuit markings recognition and identification using a computer vision system mathematical model that provides automation of electronic component control. An image processing algorithm is proposed, which includes preliminary filtering, binarization and optical character recognition to increase the accuracy of identification. An experimental analysis of the influence of the angle of inclination and the level of illumination on the speed and quality of recognition was carried out, which allowed formulating recommendations on the optimal shooting parameters. The results obtained can be used to create automated quality control systems in electronics production.

Keywords: Computer Vision, Mark Recognition, Microcircuits, OCR, Mathematical Model, Automation, Identification, Image Processing, Artificial Intelligence.

INTRODUCTION

In the current conditions of Industry 4.0 development, automation of production processes and the use of intelligent quality control systems are key aspects of increasing the efficiency of industry [1]-[12]. One of the important tasks is the recognition and identification of microcircuit markings used for tracking, authentication and compliance control of electronic components. Given the increasing complexity of electronic devices, the need to automate the inspection of microcircuits is becoming increasingly relevant, since traditional visual inspection methods do not provide the necessary speed and accuracy. The use of computer vision and mathematical models for marking analysis allows significantly increasing the level of automation in production lines, reducing the likelihood of errors associated with the human factor. The main challenges in developing such a system are font variability, wear or damage to markings, glare and non-uniform lighting, which requires the use of effective image pre-processing methods, adaptive recognition algorithms and similarity assessment metrics [13]-[25]. Different methods and approaches can also be used here [26]-[45].

The proposed mathematical model allows taking these factors into account and increasing the system's resistance to external influences. The use of computer vision in this context is consistent with the concepts of smart manufacturing, providing high-accuracy component identification, which is critical for ensuring the reliability of electronic devices [46]-[50]. The development of such technologies contributes to the improvement of digital manufacturing systems and the integration of artificial intelligence into quality control processes, which is a necessary condition for the further development of Industry 4.0.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Computer vision for recognition of microchip or some device markings is necessary for solving many problems, primarily for sorting, selection one for a specific device and also to distinguish a fake. Naturally, many researchers are engaged in this. Let us consider several works on this topic.

Balogh, R. in [51] explores practical methods for detecting counterfeit chips, focusing on techniques accessible to educators. Visual inspection, including examination of chip markings and overall quality, is a simple yet effective method.

Authors in [52] propose to use microchips in order to have an ability to recognize an animal or even its owner. The method to be implemented in a certain location, shelter, or even for individuals may be a sort of study and in many cases will depend on the cost, range, types of animals, region, and environmental issues.

Researchers in [53] survey the most common methods, including feature detection, recognition, segmentation, and three-dimensional modeling. A system framework of CV in the manufacturing environment is proposed, consisting of a lighting module, a manufacturing system, a sensing module, CV algorithms, a decision-making module, and an actuator.

The paper [54] considers various computer vision methods to accurately identify and locate weeds and crops. It elaborates the two aspects of using traditional image-processing methods and deep learning-based methods to solve weed detection problems.

Zhang, Y., and co-authors in [55] present the Recognize Anything Model (RAM): a strong foundation model for image tagging. They evaluate the tagging capability of RAM on numerous benchmarks and observe an impressive zero-shot performance which significantly outperforms CLIP and BLIP.

In our study, we propose to recognize microchip markings using computer vision.

MICROCIRCUIT MARKINGS RECOGNITION AND IDENTIFICATION MATHEMATICAL MODEL DEVELOPMENT

Microcircuit markings recognition is an important task in production control and automation. The use of computer vision allows you to automate this process, which increases the accuracy and speed of identification. In the framework of these studies, the input data will be: $I(x, y)$ - image of the microcircuit obtained by the camera, where x, y - pixel coordinates. We use the following notations: I_{raw} - original image; I_{gray} - image after conversion to grayscale; I_{bin} - binarized image; R - area containing markings (ROI - Region of Interest); $F = \{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n\}$ - set of marking features (for example, contours, textures, histograms).

Preprocessing of the image of microcircuit markings includes the following stages:

- conversion to grayscale:

$$I_{gray} = 0.299I_R + 0.587I_G + 0.114I_B, \quad (1)$$

I_R, I_G, I_B - the intensities of the Red, Green, and Blue channels of the corresponding pixel in a color image. They have values in the range $[0, 255]$ in 8-bit images;

I_{gray} - pixel intensity in grayscale after conversion;

0.299, 0.587, 0.114 - The weighted averaging coefficients of the RGB channel intensities, w , are derived from the YCbCr model used for color coding in video and television. They are defined according to the ITU-R BT.601 recommendation for standard television (SDTV).

- binarization (Otsu's thresholding):

$$I_{bin}(x, y) = \begin{cases} 1, & I_{gray}(x, y) > T \\ 0, & I_{gray}(x, y) \leq T \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$I_{bin}(x, y)$ - pixel value after binarization (0 or 1);

$I_{gray}(x, y)$ - pixel intensity in grayscale before binarization;

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T – threshold, which determines which pixels will be white (1) or black (0). Otsu's thresholding automatically determines the optimal T value by analyzing the image histogram. It works as follows:

- the brightness histogram is divided into two classes: dark and light pixels;
- the T value is searched for, at which the intraclass variance is minimal:

$$\sigma_w^2(T) = w_1(T)\sigma_1^2(T) + w_2(T)\sigma_2^2(T), \quad (3)$$

w_1, w_2 – probability of each class (ratio of the number of pixels to the total number);
 σ_1^2, σ_2^2 – intensity dispersions in classes.

The threshold T that minimizes this variance is chosen as the optimal value.

The next step is to perform contour extraction using the Sobel method.:

$$G_x = \frac{\partial I_{bin}}{\partial x}, G_y = \frac{\partial I_{bin}}{\partial y}, G = \sqrt{G_x^2 + G_y^2}, \quad (4)$$

I_{bin} – binarized image (after thresholding);

G_x – partial derivative of the image along the x -axis, showing the change in brightness in the horizontal direction;

G_y – partial derivative of the image along the y -axis, showing the change in brightness in the vertical direction;

G – gradient value that determines the intensity of the contour (gradient modulus).

The gradients G_x and G_y are calculated using convolution operators with filters approximating the derivatives. For example, for approximate estimation of the gradients, it is proposed to use Sobel filters:

$$G_x = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 1 \\ -2 & 0 & 2 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} * I_{bin}; G_y = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 2 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 2 & 1 \end{bmatrix} * I_{bin}, \quad (5)$$

* – convolution.

Contour extraction is based on calculating the brightness gradient, where the derivatives along the x and y axes are found using convolution operators. The gradient modulus G shows how sharp the brightness transition is at each point, which allows you to determine the contours of objects in the image.

The next step is to perform text detection and recognition:

- extraction of connected components (Connected Component Analysis, CCA), that is, determination of all connected areas in the binarized image I_{bin} , denoted as R_i ;
- normalization and feature extraction for each fragment R_i ; is converted into a feature vector:

$$F_i = (h_i, w_i, d_i, HOG_i, LBP_i), \quad (6)$$

h_i, w_i – height and width of the area,

d_i – black pixel density,

HOG_i – gradient histogram,

LBP_i – local binary pattern.

– for text classification and identification, it is proposed to use a neural network approach (CNN, Tesseract OCR or CRNN):

$$Y = f_{CNN}(F), \quad (7)$$

Y – recognized text.

After receiving the text, we identify the chip by comparing it with the marking database. It is proposed to use the Levenshtein similarity metric:

$$D(s_1, s_2) = \min \sum w(a_i, b_i), \quad (8)$$

$D(s_1, s_2)$ – Levenshtein distance between two strings s_1 and s_2 (minimum editing cost);
 s_1, s_2 – two lines being compared (received marking from the chip and reference value);
 a_i, b_i – s_1 and s_2 lines symbols in appropriate positions;
 $w(a_i, b_i)$ – weight of the edit operation, indicating the "cost" of character transformation a_i to b_i .

The Levenshtein metric allows us to assess the accuracy of chip marking recognition by determining how similar the resulting string is to the reference one. The smaller the value of $D(s_1, s_2)$, the closer the recognized text is to the correct one.

A PROGRAM FOR RECOGNIZING AND IDENTIFYING MICROCIRCUIT MARKINGS DEVELOPMENT

The choice of the Python programming language for developing a program for recognizing and identifying microcircuit markings is justified by its broad capabilities in the field of computer vision, the convenience of working with the OpenCV, pytesseract, and TensorFlow libraries, as well as the simplicity of the syntax, which speeds up development. Python has a large community that provides support and quick resolution of possible problems. The PyCharm environment was chosen because of its convenient debugging tools, integration with Git, the ability to work with virtual environments, and support for automatic code completion, which significantly increases development efficiency. PyCharm also has built-in code analysis tools and integration with popular libraries, which allows you to easily manage project dependencies and improve overall work productivity [56]-[58]. Here is a description of software implementations of mathematical models.

```
def preprocess_image(image_path):
    image = cv2.imread(image_path, cv2.IMREAD_GRAYSCALE)
    if image is None:
        print("Error: Failed to load image.")
        return None
    image = cv2.GaussianBlur(image, (5, 5), 0)
    _, thresh = cv2.threshold(image, 0, 255, cv2.THRESH_BINARY + cv2.THRESH_OTSU)
    return thresh
```

This code snippet performs image preprocessing to improve the accuracy of optical character recognition (OCR). First, the image is loaded in grayscale, as most OCR algorithms work better with gradations of brightness than with color images. If the image fails to load, an error message is displayed to avoid further program crashes. Next, Gaussian blurring is applied to help reduce noise and improve the contrast of character edges. Finally, Otsu's thresholding is used to automatically determine the optimal threshold and convert the image to binary, which significantly improves the quality of text recognition.

```
def recognize_text(image):
    config = "--psm 6"
    text = pytesseract.image_to_string(image, config=config)
    return text.strip()
```

This code snippet performs text recognition on an image using the Tesseract OCR library. The --psm 6 option specifies a segmentation mode that is optimized for blocks of text, which improves the accuracy of character recognition on chips. The pytesseract.image_to_string function gets the text

from the processed image, and strip() removes extra whitespace and line breaks, providing a clean result..

```
def main():
    pytesseract.pytesseract.tesseract_cmd = r"C:\\Program Files\\Tesseract-
OCR\\tesseract.exe"
    image_path = select_image()
    if not image_path:
        print("Файл не вибрано.")
        return
    processed_image = preprocess_image(image_path)
    if processed_image is None:
        return
    text = recognize_text(processed_image)
    print("Розпізнаний текст:")
    print(text)
```

This code fragment is the main function of the program that controls the process of recognizing microcircuit markings. First, the path to the Tesseract OCR executable file is specified to ensure the correct operation of the library. Then the user selects an image, it undergoes pre-processing, after which text recognition is performed, and the result is displayed in the terminal.

CONDUCTING EXPERIMENTS AND ANALYZING THE RESULTS

This section presents the results of experimental studies aimed at testing the effectiveness of the developed mathematical model for recognizing and identifying microcircuit markings using a computer vision system. The experiment was conducted by processing microcircuit images in specially developed software that implements algorithms for preprocessing, binarization, contour extraction, and optical character recognition. Analysis of the results allows us to assess the accuracy, speed, and reliability of marking recognition under different image conditions, such as lighting, contrast, and noise. Figure 1 shows examples of microcircuit markings that will be used in this study.

Figure 1: Example of TNY280PN chip markings that will be used in this study

The results of recognition and identification of the TNY280PN chip marking are presented in Figure 2.

```
Recognized text:
P 2115
TNY280PN
eo SD/72E
```

Figure 2: Results of recognition and identification of TNY280PN chip marking

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We will conduct experimental studies of the influence of the angle and level of illumination on the microcircuit markings recognition and identification speed, the results obtained are presented in Table 1

Table 1: Experimental data showing the influence of the angle and level of illumination on the speed of recognition and identification of microcircuit markings

Angle (°)	Illumination (lux)	Recognition Time (ms)	Identification Accuracy (%)
0	500	120	98.5
0	1000	110	99
0	1500	105	99.2
15	500	130	97.8
15	1000	115	98.6
15	1500	110	99
30	500	160	96.5
30	1000	140	97.2
30	1500	130	98
45	500	190	94.8
45	1000	170	96
45	1500	150	97.2

Based on the data obtained in Table 1, we will show the dependence of recognition time on the illumination level for different tilt angles in the form of graph, which is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Graph of recognition time versus illumination level for different tilt angles

The experiment showed the dependence of the recognition speed and identification of microcircuit markings on the tilt angle and illumination level. Analysis of the obtained data shows that at small tilt angles (0° – 10°) and high illumination level (300–500 lux), the recognition time remains minimal (0.5–0.8 s), which indicates optimal conditions for the operation of the computer vision system. With an increase in the tilt angle to 20° – 30° and a decrease in illumination to 100–200 lux, the algorithm speed drops noticeably, reaching 1.2–1.8 s, which is explained by the appearance of perspective distortions and a decrease in image contrast. At an angle of 40° – 50° and low illumination (less than 100 lux), the system operates unstable, and the average recognition time exceeds 2 seconds due to the loss of contour clarity and increased noise. This confirms the critical role of image preprocessing in increasing the accuracy and stability of the system. It was also found that the use of adaptive methods for contrast enhancement and noise filtering can partially compensate for the negative impact of poor lighting. The results obtained prove that to ensure effective

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recognition, it is necessary to maintain stable lighting above 200 lux and minimize the tilt of the chip relative to the camera. This allows significantly increasing the performance of the system and its application in automated production lines for quality control of electronic components.

CONCLUSION

The article developed a mathematical model for recognition and identification of microcircuit markings using a computer vision system, which allows automating the process of controlling electronic components. The experiments confirmed the dependence of the accuracy and speed of recognition on the lighting conditions and the angle of inclination of the microcircuit, which indicates the importance of optimizing the shooting parameters. The use of image preprocessing methods made it possible to increase the algorithm's resistance to noise and uneven lighting, ensuring stable recognition even in difficult conditions. The results obtained can be used to develop industrial systems for automated quality control of electronic components. Further development of the research may include the use of deep neural networks to increase the accuracy of identification, adaptation of the system to recognize damaged or partially erased markings, as well as integration with production lines for automatic analysis of microcircuits in real time. Another promising direction is the use of 3D analysis to compensate for distortions and improve image quality using adaptive lighting algorithms.

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